

Features of Civil Law in South Sudan's Legal System

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Abstract:

Historically rooted in the English Common Law tradition following the 1899 Condominium Agreement, South Sudan's legal system is often categorized as a common law jurisdiction. However, this article argues that the contemporary legal framework, primarily shaped by the Civil Procedure Act 2007 and the Code of Criminal Procedure Act 2008, exhibit significant Civil Law features, rendering it a hybrid legal system. Through a comparative analysis, the research identifies several "sign-posts" of civil law influence that includes cassation jurisdiction, procedural anomalies, inquisitorial model in criminal matters and institutional fusion. Unlike the final appellate review of facts and law in common law systems, the South Sudanese Supreme Court exercises powers of cassation, focusing strictly on the annulment of decisions based on the application of law. It is also supported that the presence of a "right of objection" against interlocutory rulings and the exclusive vesting of final judgment reviews in the Supreme Court diverge from standard common law practices in neighbouring East African states. In criminal matters, the system deviates from the adversarial model by granting magistrates investigative powers, vesting the court with the authority to draft charge sheets, compounding of offences and delaying plea-taking until after the prosecution has presented evidence, a sequence reflective of the inquisitorial tradition. The overlap of political and prosecutorial roles within the Ministry of Justice mirrors continental European structures rather than the independent directorates found in most Commonwealth jurisdictions. The article concludes that recognizing this hybridity is essential for law students, researchers, and legal practitioners to navigate the complexities of South Sudan's judiciary effectively, particularly within the context of East African Community (EAC) litigation and cross-border legal practice.

Keywords: Civil Law, Inquisitorial and Adversarial Systems, Cassation, Right of Objection, Common Law, Hybridity.

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1. INTRODUCTION

South Sudan legal system is based on common law as opposed to civil law given the colonial history of our country. Common law system is buttressed in s 7(2) of Civil Procedure Act, 2007 which provides that in cases not provided by any law, the court shall act according to Southern Sudan judicial precedents, custom and principles of justice, equity and good conscience. South Sudan, albeit being common law country, there are features of civil law in its legal system. Civil law has its origin in Roman Law, as codified in the Corpus Juris Civilis of Justinian¹ with the main feature of being contained in civil codes, which are described as a “systematic, authoritative, and guiding statute of broad coverage.

Common law on the other hand evolved in England since around the 11th century and was later adopted in the USA, Canada, Australia, New Zealand and other countries of the British Commonwealth. The most obvious distinction between civil law and common law systems is that a civil law system is a codified system, whereas the common law is not created by means of legislation but is based mainly on case law. The principle is that earlier judicial decisions, usually of the higher courts, made in a similar case, should be followed in the subsequent cases, i.e. that precedents should be respected.² This principle is known as *stare decisis* and has never been legislated but is regarded as binding by the courts, which can even decide to modify it.³

Thus, Common Law consists of the following elements: (i) it is judge-made law, as opposed to the law in statutes; (ii) the doctrine of precedent is respected; (iii) there is an adversarial system of litigation, and (iv) procedure plays a decisive role and specific procedures must be followed especially in criminal cases whereas Civil Law on the other hand is characterized by codification; absence of the doctrine of precedent and the presumption of guilt in criminal cases. The judges in such a system involve themselves directly with litigation and can even carry on investigations.⁴

Common Law was received in Sudan following the Condominium Agreement of 1899 that granted Britain colonial administration in the then Sudan. Common law was received in the Sudan vide s 4 of Civil Justice Ordinance 1900 which stated that ‘*in cases not provided by this Ordinance, or by any other law for the time being in force, the court shall act according to justice, equity and good conscience*’.

However, Common law had been applicable in the Sudanese legal system since independence in 1956 until brought to a halt by Civil Code 1971 under Revolutionary Military Council's Government of Jaafar Nimeiri which repealed s 9 of the Civil Justice Ordinance, 1929. The new Civil Code 1971 containing 917 sections introduced Civil Law features into the Sudan for the first time. The new Civil Code 1971, drafted by Egyptian

¹ Prof. Caslav Pejovic, *Civil Law and Common Law: Two Different Paths Leading to the Same Goal*, July 2001, Khushu University, Japan.

² Ibid.

³ Ibid.

⁴ Joe Oloka-Onyango, *An Overview of Legal System in Uganda*, May 2020, Makerere University, p.3, a Presentation at China-Africa Legal Forum November 25, 2015.

lawyers with few Sudanese lawyers brought confusion until the country reverted back to common law system following the re-enactment of Civil Procedure Act, 1974. The Regularization of Laws Act. No. 4 of 1973 repealed the 1971 Civil Code Act, the Civil Pleadings Act, 1972 and the Civil Evidence Act, 1972. It revived the laws that were repealed by the foregoing Acts, viz. the Civil Justice Ordinance 1929 except for the justice, equity and good conscience provision (section 9) and a few other provisions and chapters.⁵ It should be noted that the current sections 6 and 7 of Civil Procedure Act, 2007 are a replica of sections 6 and 7 of Civil Procedure Act, 1974 and ss 3 and 5 of Civil Justice Ordinance 1900 and s 9 of Civil Justice Ordinance 1929 respectively.

By 1983, Sharia law was introduced into Sudan influencing Sudan's legal system until South Sudan broke away 2011. However, during the SPLM/A liberation struggle, secular laws were introduced and became applicable in SPLM/A controlled areas e.g Civil Procedure Act, 2003 became applicable in SPLM/A controlled areas. By 2007, after the formation of autonomous Government of Southern Sudan following Comprehensive Peace Agreement, the current Civil Procedure Act, 2007 was enacted by Southern Sudan Legislative Assembly and it is applicable law today.

This article argues that South Sudan legal system contains features of Civil Law and it will highlight these features in Civil Procedure Act, 2007 and Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 respectively. It also argues that South Sudan's Legal System is a mixture of civil and common law systems thus making it a hybrid legal system.

The purpose of this article is to enable law students, researchers and legal practitioners particularly those with exclusive common law training background acquaint themselves with the hybrid nature of South Sudan's legal system. It is also important in the context of East Africa Community litigation. This article does not purport in any way to examine the meanings and correct procedural steps of the provisions that are Civil Law oriented in our Civil Procedure Act, Code of Criminal Procedure Act or any other enactment. The article only points out the sign-posts of Civil Law features to acquaint yourself with, in South Sudan's legal system.

This article is divided into two parts: features of Civil Law in civil justice system which will be examined in the first part followed by Civil Law features in criminal justice system in the second part and finally the conclusion.

2. FEATURES OF CIVIL LAW IN CIVIL JUSTICE SYSTEM

Article 19 (1) of Transitional Constitution of South Sudan, 2011 as amended provides that an accused person is presumed innocent until his or her guilt is proved according to law. This is a well-known common law rule of presumption of innocence in criminal proceedings and it is a foundation for observance of rule of law and protection of human

⁵ Abderahman Ibrahim El Khalifa, *Development and Future of English Law and Islamic Law in Sudan*, PhD Thesis, 1988 at p.177

rights of individuals indicted with criminal charges. It is distinct from presumption of guilt followed in civil law jurisdictions.

In South Sudan, the guidance on the law to be applied in absence of express provision is found in s 7 (1) and (2) of Civil Procedure Act, 2007 stipulated in the following terms:

- (1) In matters of procedure not provided for by this Act, the Court shall apply such rules as are likely to serve the ends of justice.
- (2) In cases not provided for by any law, the Court shall act according to Southern Sudan judicial precedents, custom and principles of justice, equity and good conscience.

Despite the article 19 (1) of TCSS, 2011 as amended and s 7(2) of Civil Procedure Act, 2007 that anchor common law in our legal system, there are provisions within the Act that are civil law oriented. This Part I will first explore the civil law provisions in the Code of Civil Procedure Act, 2007 and Part II will discuss the civil law features in the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008.

a) Cassation jurisdiction of Supreme Court of South Sudan

The Supreme Court of South Sudan is statutorily seized with cassation powers of review similar to that conferred on supreme court of civil law jurisdiction for example, France, Belgium, Germany etc. The word cassation [esp in France] according to Collins English Dictionary means annulment, as of a judicial decision by a higher court. The jurisdiction of Court of Cassation is only limited to review of application of law by the lower courts and does not extend to assessment of the facts of the case. This is a stark difference with common law jurisdiction where the final appellate courts have the power to review the lower court's decision on application of the law and facts.

Section 18(2)(c) of the Civil Procedure Act 2007 provides that:

Without prejudice to the provisions of subsection (1), above the Supreme Court shall have the following powers and jurisdiction... review and cassation in respect of any civil and administrative matters arising out of or under Southern Sudan laws.

A complete Chapter XXIII of Civil Procedure Act, 2007 is devoted to cassation as a post judgment remedy to a litigant aggrieved by a decision of lower court. This will be examined in detail in next part.

The Supreme Court of the United Kingdom, formerly the House of Lords, does not, by contrast, have a cassation jurisdiction. Similarly, Judicature Act of Uganda⁶ and

⁶ S 5(1)(a) and s 6 (1) of Judicature Act, Cap.16 as amended of Uganda

Supreme Court Act of Kenya⁷, being common law jurisdictions, do not provide cassation jurisdiction.

Notwithstanding the cassation jurisdiction of the Supreme Court, the Court of Appeal on the other hand, has a peculiar jurisdiction of entertaining appeals from administrative decisions rendered by administrative authorities.⁸ This is rather surprising to a common law legal practitioner because the Court of Appeal, in common law jurisdictions, is not a court of original jurisdiction saves where it equally doubles as a constitutional court like the case of Uganda.⁹ The Court of Appeal in common law system exercises appellate jurisdiction only. This practically means that in South Sudan, a decision of a minister may be appealable to Court of Appeal by virtue of s 19(b) of the Civil Procedure Act, 2007 or Supreme Court in terms of s 20 (2) of Ministry of Legal Affairs and Constitutional Development Organization Act, 2008.

By having cassation jurisdiction of the Supreme Court of South Sudan like other Civil Law countries, this paper undoubtedly argues that South Sudan's legal system is not purely following common law but apparently a hybrid of civil and common law systems.

b) Right of objection in interlocutory decisions

The right of objection from interlocutory rulings by civil courts is unique in our jurisdiction. Interlocutory applications are always contested by lawyers to the extent that resulting rulings may be appealable to the appellate court thereby causing delays in disposal of suits. What is remarkable under s 83 of Civil Procedure Act, 2007 is that issues of law ought to be settled first before a suit is set for hearing. A ruling from an interlocutory application is not appealable unless it passes the test stipulated under s 174(1)-(10) of the Civil Procedure Act, 2007 in what is referred to as a right of objection. This should not be confused with a preliminary objection on the point of law. Section 174 of the Civil Procedure Act, 2007 quoted extensively, states as follows:

No right of objection exists against an interlocutory order before final judgement except in the following cases:

- (1) An order from which an appeal is expressly allowed by law;
- (2) An order staying or suspending the suit;
- (3) Assumption of jurisdiction;
- (4) An order capable of instantaneous execution;
- (5) An order superseding an order of reference where the arbitration award has not been

⁷ Ss 12, 13, 15, 15A, 15B of the Supreme Court Act No.7 of 2011 of Kenya

⁸ s 19(b) of the Civil Procedure Act, 2007.

⁹ Article 137 of the Constitution of Republic of Uganda.

- complied with within the time allowed by Court;
- (6) An order on an award stated in the form of a request of the opinion of the Court;
 - (7) An order modifying or correcting an award;
 - (8) An order filing or refusing to file an agreement to refer to arbitration;
 - (9) An order staying or refusing to stay a suit where there is an agreement to refer to arbitration; and,
 - (10) An order refusing to set aside the arbitration or to remit it to the arbitrators.

c) Cassation review in post-judgment remedies

Post-judgment remedial options available to a party that lost a suit are review, revision and appeal in common law jurisdictions. However, South Sudan Civil Procedure Act, 2007 presents one more post-judgment remedy by way of cassation in the circumstances,¹⁰ and review of final judgment as features of civil law procedure in our legal system. Another remedy to be explored together with cassation in this part is a right of objection,¹¹ being a post-interlocutory ruling remedy.

First, the provisions relating to cassation remedy are contained in ss 203 to 207 of the Civil Procedure Act, 2007. Cases that can be objected before Supreme Court by way of cassation are where:

- (1) Parties may object before the Supreme Court against judgements made by the Court of Appeal in the following cases:
 - (a) where the judgement objected against is based upon inconsistency with the law or a mistake as to its application or interpretation;
 - (b) where the judgement has been affected by the occurrence of an invalidity in the judgement or procedure;
- (2) Objection relating to the ownership of immovable property, shall lie before the Supreme Court.¹²

¹⁰ S 203 of the Civil Procedure Act, 2007

¹¹ 173 of the Civil Procedure Act, 2007

¹² S 203 of the Civil Procedure Act, 2007

It can certainly be discerned from the above provision that where the Court of Appeal renders judgment inconsistent with the law, or erroneous application of law or misinterpretation of the same would entitle the aggrieved party to file an objection by way of cassation to Supreme Court. Other grounds contestable by way of cassation are an occurrence of an invalidity of judgment or procedure that led to impugned judgment and ownership of immovable property.

What is unclear under s 188(3) of the Civil Procedure Act, 2007 which states that appeals against judgements of a Court of Appeal shall lie with the Supreme Court, is whether such appeals from Court of Appeal to Supreme Court may be on grounds of mixed law and fact or of law only.

Secondly, another feature of Civil Law in our jurisdiction is an exclusive vesting of review of final judgment to the Supreme Court under s 18(2)(c) and chapter XXIV under ss 208 to 212 of the Civil Procedure Act, 2007. This means that no any other court in our land that exercises the power of review of the judgment except the Supreme Court. The common grounds for review of a judgment are discovery of fraud and discovery of new evidence which was not readily available during trial despite an exercise of due diligence.

Thus, the court that rendered judgment requiring review shall be the same court that shall entertain an application for review of the judgment in common law jurisdiction.¹³ This is quite an asymmetrical position with South Sudan where a power of review of judgment is a preserve of the Supreme Court.

The civil procedure laws in either Uganda or Kenya do not have provisions on right of objection. They have right of appeal. A right of appeal is a creature of statute in common law jurisdictions and therefore, whenever a statute expressly provides that a party against whom an interlocutory order is made has a right of appeal, then that party may appeal the order.

The cassation jurisdiction of South Sudan's Supreme Court, cassation as post judgment remedy and review of by final judgment by Supreme Court are indicators of Civil Law features. The common law countries do not have cassation or right of objection.

d) Protest of acts

A protest for non-payment is a formal, often notarial, legal declaration that a negotiable instrument—such as a bill of exchange or promissory note—has been dishonored. It serves as official evidence that payment was demanded and refused, which is required to hold other parties, like endorsers, liable.

In South Sudan, protests of bill of exchange or promissory notes are administered by court clerks directly pursuant to sub-rule (1) of Rule 4 of Civil Procedure Rules, a feature reflective of civil law. Court clerks are supposed to discharge administrative

¹³ Order XLVI of Civil Procedure Rules S.I 71-1of Uganda

function only by assisting judges and not judicial functions because they are not law graduates. To entrust them[clerks] with a judicial functional of protesting or noting bill of exchange so dishonored by way of legislation is utterly misplaced. The Civil Procedure Act, 2007 under rule 4 stipulates that the High Court judge shall appoint in such Courts of the Circuit as he or she thinks necessary a person to act as protest clerk for the purpose of presenting, protesting and registering protests of bill or promissory notes. It further states that where the holder desires to protest an Act for non-acceptance or non-payment he or she shall deliver it to the Court within whose local limits of jurisdiction where the Act is payable to the person against whom the protest is to be made has a dwelling place or a place of business and the Court shall not, if the prescribed formalities have been complied with, refuse to make the protest, except where the holder applies for protest for non-payment when the Act is not then due.¹⁴

In contrast with other purely common law jurisdictions, for example, in Uganda, a protest of foreign bill is notarized by a notary public not a court clerk. Thus, a protest must contain a copy of the bill, and must be signed by the notary making it and must specify— (a) the person at whose request the bill is protested; (b) the place and date of protest, the cause or reason for protesting the bill, the demand made, and the answer given, if any, or the fact that the drawer acceptor could not be found.¹⁵

In addition, the Bills of Exchange Act Cap.27 of Kenya has similar provision with that of Uganda regarding the procedure of noting or protesting a bill. This similarity hinges on a shared inheritance of English law in Kenya and Uganda. Thus, s 51(7) of Bills of Exchange Act Cap.27 of Kenya provides in exact provision as that of Uganda above. This means that a bill has to be noted or protested by an advocate licensed as a notary public or magistrate or registrars of court by *virtute officii* under s 2 of Notaries Public Act Cap.20 laws of Uganda.

It is therefore submitted that the Code of Civil Procedure Act, 2007 by vesting the procedure of protesting a dishonoured bill or promissory notes on court clerks is a feature of civil law and not common law tradition.

e) Civil proceedings not provided in Civil Procedure Act, 2007

In an eye-catching lacuna in our Civil Procedure Act,2007 and being an incidental matter to this article, the following procedural matters are not provided in the Act:

- a) Counterclaim
- b) Summary Procedure or especially endorsed plaint
- c) Garnishee proceedings
- d) Security for costs
- e) Test suit
- f) Consolidation of suits

¹⁴ Sub-rule (2) of Rule 4 of Civil Procedure Rules of South Sudan.

¹⁵ S 50(7) of Bills of Exchange Act, Cap.68, Laws of Uganda

- g) Taxation of costs
- h) revision
- i) Notice of motion, originating summons and chamber summons
- j) Registrars and their judicial roles

3. FEATURES OF CIVIL LAW IN CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM

a) Cassation jurisdiction of Supreme Court in criminal matters

The Supreme Court of South Sudan has similar review and cassation jurisdiction in criminal cases like in civil matters. This is provided by s 10(c) of the Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 which states that the Supreme Court of Southern Sudan shall have the following powers and competence: be a Court of review and cassation in respect of any criminal, civil and or administrative matters arising out of or under the laws of Southern Sudan. A Court of Cassation is the supreme court for civil and criminal matters in France.¹⁶ The word 'cassation' means quashing or annulling. A ruling by a court of cassation quashes a judicial decision on a point of law. Over 20 countries have specialized courts of cassation including Armenia, Austria, Belgium, Egypt, France, Greece, Haiti, Iraq, Senegal, Turkey, Japan, Netherlands, Indonesia, Vietnam etc.¹⁷

It is therefore submitted that the Supreme Court of South Sudan, having cassation jurisdiction, is a feature of continental law system.

b) The fusion of political role of the Minister of Justice and Constitutional Affairs and prosecutorial power vested in Directorate of Public Prosecutions

The Transitional Constitution provides that the Minister of Justice and Constitutional Affairs shall be the chief Legal Advisor and the prosecuting authority at all levels of government, and shall perform such other functions of legal nature as may be prescribed by law.¹⁸ This is echoed by Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 which stipulates that the Directorate of Public Prosecutions shall consist of the:

1. Minister,
2. The Under-Secretary of the Ministry, and,
3. The directors of Specialized Units, as well as the Directors of Legal Administrations in the States, all of whom shall be deemed to be Public Prosecution Attorneys.¹⁹

The Ministry of Legal Affairs and Constitutional Development Organization Act, 2008 establishes a Directorate of Public Prosecutions tasked with criminal prosecutions in the

¹⁶ <https://www.en.wikipedia.org>

¹⁷ <https://judiciariesworldwide.fjc.gov>

¹⁸ Art 135(2) of the Transitional Constitution of South Sudan, 2011 as amended

¹⁹ S 22(2) of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008

country.²⁰ What these provisions practically mean is that the Minister, Undersecretary and Director of Public Prosecutions are all involved in decisions of public prosecutions. Needless to say, that as the Minister of Justice and Constitutional Affairs sits with his or her colleagues in the cabinet meeting, he or she is also their criminal prosecutor in any event of contravention of the criminal statutes.

In common law jurisdictions, the Attorney General and Directorate of Public Prosecutions are independent from the Ministry of Justice and they are only accountable to parliament. The role of the Ministry of Justice in common law countries is confined to administration of justice and the political role to the cabinet. This paper thus, argues that the fusion of political role of the Minister of Justice and Constitutional Affairs with Directorate of Public Prosecutions and Advocate General is a feature of civil law that common law lawyers in South Sudan should take note of it.

c) Power of investigation of criminal offenses

The criminal investigative power conferred upon magistrate under ss 52 and 216 of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 is an indication that South Sudan legal system is hybrid in nature. The authority to conduct criminal investigations is vested in Police, Public Prosecution Attorney or Magistrate in terms of 52 of Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 which states that:

- (1) Investigations shall be conducted by the police under the supervision and directive of the Public Prosecution Attorney, or in the absence of the Public Prosecution Attorney, the Magistrate, as the case may be, in accordance with the provisions of this Act.
- (2) The Public Prosecution Attorney or Magistrate may exercise the powers of investigation, or complete the investigation himself or herself, where necessity requires.

Similarly, the investigative power of Public Prosecution Attorney or Magistrate is stipulated under s 216 of Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 which states that:

If a Public Prosecution Attorney or Magistrate taking cognizance of an alleged offence is not satisfied that the offence has been committed, or if for any other reason he or she deems it expedient to do so, he or she may either himself or herself make an investigation into the case or direct the police to do so. Such investigation shall be conducted so far as may be in the manner and with the powers with which an investigation under Chapter VII is conducted, and shall, if the police have

²⁰ s 8(1) of the Ministry of Legal Affairs and Constitutional Development Organization Act, 2008

already investigated the case, be deemed to be a continuation of that investigation.

The power to conduct criminal investigations ought to solely vest with executive arm of government through public prosecutions attorneys and police. It is improper for magistrate court to involve in the process of investigation by virtue of ss 52 and 216 of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 as seen above. The judiciary is an independent organ of government²¹ and it should deal with trials only rather than getting tangled in criminal investigations.

It is submitted that by vesting criminal investigation on a magistrate in the absence of public prosecution attorney under ss 52 and 216 of Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008, is indication of Civil Law in our legal system. In civil law jurisdictions generally, the court is inquisitorial in trial including investigations as opposed to adversarial system in common jurisdiction where courts are only involved during trial stage.

d) Power to draft charge sheet

The procedure of non-summary trial under s 224 of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 is totally alien to common law jurisdictions in as far as charge sheet and plea taking is concerned. A charge is a formal accusation of any offence as framed therein as a preliminary step in prosecution and includes any head of charge when the charge contains more than one head.²² A charge sheet according to Oxford Dictionary of Law means a document in which an officer at a police station records an accusation against a suspect. It normally also gives details of his name and those of his accusers, who should sign the sheet.²³

It is a duty of magistrates and courts in South Sudan to frame or draft the charge sheet.²⁴ In order to record the charge and fill the charge sheet, the magistrate shall ascertain the satisfactions of all the elements and conditions required by law.²⁵ It simply means that it is the duty court to draft a charge sheet not the police or Director of Public Prosecutions.

The duty of Police or Director of Public Prosecutions with regard to framing a charge against a suspect is simply stating the provision of Penal Code Act or any other penal enactment allegedly violated for purpose of investigations. The mandate of Directorate of Public Prosecutions (DPP) in relation to criminal prosecutions is to supervise investigations and take cognizance of and prosecute all criminal cases at the GoSS and State levels in accordance with applicable law.²⁶ Similarly, the DPP has the

²¹ s 6(2) of the Judiciary Act, 2008

²² S 5 of Code of Criminal procedure Act, 2008.

²³ Oxford Dictionary of Law 5th ed, p.75, Oxford University Press.

²⁴ s 224(2)(f) of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008.

²⁵ S 233(1) of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008.

²⁶ S 8(2)(b) of the Ministry of Legal Affairs and Constitutional Development Organization Act, 2008.

mandate to supervise the progress of criminal cases, including, but not limited to directing or executing the investigation, *framing of the charges*, and prosecution of cases on behalf of the Government and, during four years into the Interim Period at the State level, before the criminal courts of Southern Sudan.²⁷

The powers of Crime Police Unit on the other hand does not include framing or charge or drafting of charge sheet but only limited to among others, conduct investigations under directive of DPP and presenting criminal cases to court.²⁸

To understand the sequence of trial procedure in South Sudan, s 224(2)(a) to (m) of Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 is quoted in its entirety and it stipulates that:

- (1) The procedures set forth under this section shall be observed by the Magistrates and the Courts in the trial of cases non-summarily.
- (2) The Magistrate or Court shall follow the trial procedure in the following sequence—
 - (a) Verifying the basic evidence about the accused, the witnesses and the subject of the case;
 - (b) Hearing the prosecution opening speech, statements of the inquirer and the complainant, if any, and discussion of the same;
 - (c) Reply of the accused to the prosecution;
 - (d) Evidence of the prosecution, and discussion of the same;
 - (e) Examination of the accused;
 - (f) Framing of the charge, by drafting the charge sheet, where the Court deems it appropriate;
 - (g) Addressing the accused, with the charge, and his or her reply thereto;
 - (h) Hearing the evidence of the defence;
 - (i) Any procedure in evidence, as the Court may allow;
 - (j) Admission of final pleadings, if any, for the proprietor or private right, the prosecution and then the defence;
 - (k) Delivery of the decision of conviction or acquittal;
 - (l) Hearing reasons of mitigation or aggravation of

²⁷ S 23 (1)(a) of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008.

²⁸ S 27(2) of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008.

- penalty; and
- (m) The final orders in judgment.
 - (3) Where the accused admits the offence, upon his or her reply, to the prosecution, the Court may frame the charge, without he or she hearing the evidence of the prosecution.
 - (4) Where the accused denies the offence or the Court deemed it necessary, and notwithstanding his or her admission, that it is most appropriate to hear the evidence, the Court shall call for the prosecution evidence, and proceed with the rest of the procedure.

In jurisdictions following common law tradition such as Uganda, framing a charge and drafting charge sheet are a responsibility of Director of Public Prosecutions for indictable offences. All indictments shall be in the name of and subject to s 135 of Trial and Indictment Act, signed by the Director of Public Prosecutions.²⁹ In cases triable by magistrate court, the charge sheet should be signed by the police officer who brings the charge and the magistrate should not accept and proceed with the charge until it is signed.³⁰

By vesting power to frame a charge and drafting of charge sheet on court under s 224 (2) (f) of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008, it is submitted that this is a feature of Civil Law in our legal system. By contrast, the role of court in common law jurisdiction is to facilitate the plea taking of accused and making a finding on *prima facie* case.

e) The stage of trial where plea taking begins

A plea is formal answer to the charge by accused person. A plea may be of guilt or not guilty. Under s 224(2)(g) Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 the accused person takes the plea. It is the 7th stage in the trial procedure. The plea taking of accused person happens after conclusion of prosecution evidence and examination of the accused under Code of Criminal Procedure Act. 2008. It is at this stage that the trial court will draft a charge sheet and address it to accused in order to take his or her plea.³¹

As per the outline of trial procedure under s 224 (2) (a) to (m) of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008, you will realise that the 7th stage of plea taking in South Sudan is equivalent to finding of *prima facie* case against the accused in common law

²⁹ Ssekaana Musa, Criminal Procedure and Practice in Uganda, 2010, p.226; s 135 of Trial and Indictment Act, Cap.99, Laws of Uganda.

³⁰ Uganda vs S.Byaruhanga [1975] HCB 258.

³¹ S 224(2) (g) of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008.

jurisdictions. Thus, the trial procedure in South Sudan in summary is that: first, that the prosecution will lead evidence against accused, the court then examines the accused. Secondly, court drafts the charge sheet and asks the accused to take a plea. Thirdly, if the accused pleads not guilty, he or she will be called to his or her defence. Fourthly, conviction and ultimately, the sentence.

In common law jurisdictions, plea taking is the first step of trial procedure. Ordinarily under the common law system, the police or DPP draft(s) the charge sheet and arraign the accused person in court to take a plea. The signed charge sheet by DPP is submitted to court with file of investigation. The court will read a charge sheet and request the accused to take his or her plea. Once the accused pleads guilty, then the court enters conviction and a sentence. But if the accused pleads not guilty, then it triggers the trial and the prosecution will lead evidence against the accused at this stage. At the conclusion of prosecution evidence, the court will make a ruling on *prima facie* case, and if the accused has a case to answer, then the accused will be informed of right to defend himself by calling witnesses.

The order of non-summary trial under the s 224 of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 shows that the nature of trial is inquisitorial due to the fact the court first inquired into the alleged offence. Should the court be satisfied that there exists a *prima facie* case against the accused, the court shall draft a charge sheet and orders the accused to take a plea. This method of trial is fundamentally distinct from adversarial system and therefore, it is submitted that the entire s 224 of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 is Civil Law in nature.

f) Compounding of offences

An offence is a wrong against the society or state as a whole and it is a punishable conduct by the state in accordance with penal law. The Director of Public Prosecutions has the mandate to prosecute criminals who commit offences against society or state. Criminal law generally allows compensation to victims of criminal offence in addition to custodial sentence to an accused person. In this regard the private right of a victim of wrong is redressed through compensation and the public right is addressed through conviction and sentence.

However, an accused person, in certain circumstances of misdemeanor, may escape conviction and sentence by resorting to settlement of a criminal case through a process called 'compounding of an offence'. The rationale of compounding offenses is to encourage reconciliation, harmonious co-existence between accused and victim of wrong and also to reduce backlog of cases in court. Compoundability of an offence leads to acquittal of the accused person and shall not be prosecuted of the same offense compounded.

According to s 5 of Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 defines "compound" to mean to agree not to prosecute in return for a consideration or otherwise. It simply means to settle by money payment in lieu of other liability. In the Indian case of *Gian Singh v*

State of Punjab,³² wherein the constitution bench had observed that compounding powers should be exercised by the court considering the social impact of the crime in question vis a vis its individual impact, as a decision criterion for quashing power in such cases.

Compounding an offence in our criminal system is buttressed by article 122(5)(d) of the Transitional Constitution of South Sudan, 2011 as amended which states that in adjudicating cases of both civil and criminal nature, the court shall, subject to the law, apply, inter alia the following principles... voluntary reconciliation agreements between the parties shall be recognized and enforced. In addition, this principle is echoed under s 6(i) of Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 which states that voluntary reconciliatory agreements between parties shall be recognized and enforced.

Thus, s 45 of the Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 provides for compounding of offenses and states as follow:

- (1) No offence shall be compounded except as provided by this section.
- (2) The compounding of an offence under this section shall have the effect of an acquittal of the accused.
- (3) The offences punishable under the sections of the Penal Code described in the first two columns of the table attached hereto as Schedule I, may be compounded by the persons mentioned in the third column of that table.
- (4) When any offence is compoundable under this section, the abetment of such offence or an attempt to commit such offence (when such attempt is in itself an offence) may be compounded in like manner.
- (5) When the person who would otherwise be competent to compound an offence under this section is a juvenile, invalid, an idiot or a lunatic, any person competent as his or her guardian may compound the offence.
- (6) The offences mentioned in Chapter I of the table attached as Schedule I, may be compounded without the leave of any authority at any time before the accused person is convicted by a County Court Magistrate or committed for trial to a High Court.
- (7) The offences mentioned in Chapter II of the table

³² (2012) 10 SCC 303.

attached as Schedule I, may be compounded before the County Court Magistrate who has convicted the accused person or committed for trial, only with the consent of a Magistrate who has jurisdiction to try the accused person for the offence or to commit him or her for trial.

Owing to poor legislative drafting or oversight by a draftsman, Schedule I referred to in s 45 of Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 is non-existent in the Act. The schedule and table of compoundable and non-compoundable offenses have been omitted in the current Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 2008 but nonetheless, it can be accessed in Code of Criminal Procedure Act, 1973 of Sudan. The examples of compoundable offenses in Penal Code Act, 2008 are: assault or use criminal force, mischief, criminal trespass, adultery, defamation, criminal intimidation etc.

The non-compoundable offences on the other hand are felonious and perpetrators deserve punishment in order to protect the society. The examples of non-compoundable offences are: rape, murder, robbery, treason etc.

Many lawyers trained in common law systems are familiar with plea bargain which is an arrangement between the prosecutor and the accused whereby the accused person pleads guilty to a lesser charge in exchange for a more lenient sentence or an agreement to drop other charges. It does not lead to acquittal of accused person but reduces the sentence of accused when pleading to lesser count. Plea bargain differs from compounding of offenses in that the former does not lead to acquittal and the latter leads to an acquittal of the accused person.

g) Trial by jury or assessors

The right to a trial by jury is unique to English and American law.³³ It is a right that stems from a distrust of judges when they were under the direct control of the king, who had absolute power.³⁴ The right to trial by jury has been significantly abridged in England, but in America it is protected by the United States Constitution and by state constitutions. In United Kingdom, the practice of trial by jury was conceived as a bulwark serving to protect the accused individual against oppressive executive action and rigid legal forms, elements which are unacceptable to current general opinion.³⁵

Trial by jury or assessors spread to commonwealth during colonization. The assessors or jurors assist the trial judge on finding of facts relative to evidence but not law. The importance of assessors was succinctly stated by Court of Appeal for Eastern Africa in the case of *Mutwiwas s/o Mangi v R*³⁶ that: one of the objects in having assessors was to assist the court on questions which might arise as to the law and customs

³³ William M.Hart and Roderick D. Blanchard, *Litigation and Trial Practice*, 6th ed, 2007 at p.11

³⁴ *Ibid.*

³⁵ Ssekaan Musa, *Criminal Procedure and Practice in Uganda*, 2010, Law Africa Publishing (U) Ltd, p.301, *Also Morris and Read, Indirect Rule and the Search for Justice* Oxford Clarendon Press 1972.p.322

³⁶ (1935)2 EACA 66.

of any tribe, caste or community. The court further pointed out that the provision was made by the legislature for Europeans administering justice i.e the customs in a foreign land whereas there was deficiency in their knowledge of the customs and habits of the parties and witnesses appearing before them and hence were deficient in judging the demeanor of the witness in the witness box. It was thus necessary for them to be assisted by native assessors possessing such knowledge and judgment as a safeguard to the natives accused of crime and guarantee that their own customs and habits of life which were alien to colonial judges were misunderstood.

South Sudan does not have mandatory system of trial by assessors in the criminal justice system. It is noted that in land cases, trial by assessors is provided by Land Act, 2009: It states (1) subject to the provisions of Article 127(e) of the Constitution, there shall be established a Land Division in the High Court in every State consisting of a Judge and two assessors. (2) One assessor shall be representative of the Traditional authority and possessing a good knowledge of customary law and practices related to land.³⁷ It is justifiable in our criminal justice system to have trial by assessors given the diverse nature of cultural norms. A judge of a particular tribe may not be conversant with norms and traditions of local people he or she may be assigned to in the country thus making the trial by assessors more compelling.

4. CONCLUSION

The argument for hybrid nature our legal system is nonetheless more compelling and imperative than South Sudan being a purely common law system. As shown in this article, procedural laws have been explored and signposts of civil law features are identified. In our civil justice system, proceedings like cassation, objection and protests reflect civil law system and do not feature in common law systems. It is unfortunate that important civil procedure concepts are left out in Code of Civil Procedure Act, 2007 for example, revision, counterclaim, consolidation of suits, garnishee proceedings, test suits and security for costs.

When such matters arise in litigation without supporting legal provision, advocates usually invoke the discretionary power of court under s 328(2) of Code of Civil Procedure Act, 2007 which states that nothing in this Act shall be deemed to limit or otherwise affect the inherent power of the Court to make such order as may be necessary, for the ends of justice, or to prevent abuse of the process of the Court. On the other hand, in criminal proceedings, powers of inquiry and taking cognizance of criminal offences by magistrates, drafting of charge sheet by court, sequence of trial procedure including plea taking, compounding of offences, trial of capital offences without assessors exhibit civil law nature.

³⁷ S 99(1) (2) of Land Act, 2009.

It is imperative to lawyers trained outside South Sudan particularly in common law countries to take precautions while conducting trial in South Sudan. Additionally, there is a practice dilemma for South Sudanese law graduates or law students from Egypt, Morocco, Ethiopia etc that follow civil law system, to embrace the common law concept of precedent in our practice.

It is the author's hope that this article will not only chart guidance on hybridity of our legal system but also provides researchers, students, judicial officers and legal practitioners, particularly those from pure common jurisdictions, a reflection of some topics explored herein.